

Comparing JEFF-4.0 and Legacy JEFF Libraries in Fuel Depletion Benchmark Studies

Luca Fiorito^{1,*}, Pablo Romojaro¹, Alexey Stankovskiy¹

¹SCK CEN, Boeretang 190, 2400 Mol, Belgium

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ABSTRACT

Accurate nuclear data are essential for reliable predictions of spent nuclear fuel composition. This work evaluates the performance of the recently released JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library in UO₂ fuel depletion calculations, focusing on its predictive accuracy for actinide and fission-product inventories. Calculations were performed with the Monte Carlo burnup code SERPENT 2.2 for two representative test cases: a simplified TMI-1 PWR pin-cell model and the REBUS experimental benchmark. The results obtained with JEFF-4.0 were compared against previous JEFF releases (JEFF-3.1.2 and JEFF-3.3) and major ENDF/B evaluations (ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, and ENDF/B-VIII.1).

Compared to previous JEFF releases, JEFF-4.0 shows improved consistency and close agreement with experimental data in this case study for several key nuclides, including burnup indicators ¹³⁷Cs and ¹⁴⁸Nd. Nonetheless, systematic deviations persist for specific fission products and minor actinides, indicating areas where further evaluation refinements may be needed.

A statistical normalization method was applied to quantify and visualize discrepancies among isotopic predictions from different libraries, allowing a model-independent assessment of trends across libraries. The methodology developed here demonstrates that standardized comparisons of predicted inventories across nuclear data libraries, even when applied to mock-up pin-cell calculations, provide a practical diagnostic tool to identify and interpret discrepancies prior to experimental validation.

Keywords: burnup, nuclide inventory, nuclear data, REBUS, JEFF

1. INTRODUCTION

The accuracy of nuclear data remains one of the major sources of uncertainty in the modelling and simulation of nuclear systems. At the back-end of the fuel cycle, this uncertainty directly impacts the reliability of spent fuel composition predictions. In waste management applications, accurate nuclear data are required to optimize criticality-safety margins, support burnup credit methodologies, and ensure robust assessments of decay heat and radiological source terms arising from neutron and γ -ray emissions. To address these needs, continuous improvements in nuclear data evaluations are pursued by international projects such as JEFF and ENDF/B [1, 2]. In particular, the JEFF nuclear data project has recently devoted significant effort to enhancing the quality of data for fission products and actinides that play a key role in spent fuel characterization. The latest release, JEFF-4.0 (released in 2025), incorporates numerous updates, including the adoption of TENDL-based evaluations [3] for fission-product cross sections, and newly generated fission yield evaluations for the thermal fission of ²³⁵U and ²³⁹Pu [4]. These developments are expected to improve the consistency of predicted inventories across nuclide chains.

In this work, we investigate the predictive performance of the JEFF-4.0 library in burnup calculations, using the nuclide composition of spent nuclear fuel as the main observable. The results are compared

*luca.fiorito@sckcen.be

with those obtained using previous JEFF versions — JEFF-3.1.2 and JEFF-3.3 — as well as with other evaluation projects, including ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, and ENDF/B-VIII.1.

The comparison is first performed on a simplified single-pin depletion model representative of UO_2 fuel irradiated in a pressurized water reactor (PWR). This reference case allows the identification of systematic trends and nuclide-specific deviations attributable only to nuclear data differences. In the second part of the paper, the same methodology is applied to experimental post-irradiation data from the REBUS PWR fuel sample [5], to evaluate the agreement between predictions and measured nuclide inventories.

Through this analysis, we aim to quantify the improvements introduced in JEFF-4.0 and to identify nuclides and reaction channels where further development of evaluated nuclear data could have the greatest impact on the accuracy of spent fuel characterization.

2. CASE STUDIES: THE TMI PIN-CELL AND THE REBUS BENCHMARK

The predictive performances of the nuclear data libraries were compared by modelling depletion problems with different nuclear data evaluations, while keeping all other model input parameters unchanged. This approach isolates the effect of the nuclear data from those of modelling assumptions or system-specific conditions.

2.1. The TMI-1 Pin-Cell Model

As a first test case, a simplified two-dimensional model representative of a UO_2 fuel pin from the Three Mile Island Unit 1 (TMI-1) pressurized water reactor (PWR) was adopted [6]. The geometry and operating conditions are based on the OECD/NEA Uncertainty Analysis in Modelling (UAM) benchmark, specifically Exercise I-1b “PWR Pin-Cell” [7, 8]. The benchmark provides a well-defined reference configuration adopted in many burnup analyses [9, 10, 11], making it suitable for evaluating the isolated impact of nuclear data variations.

Fuel depletion was modelled up to 60 GWd/t, a representative discharge burnup for modern PWR fuels. All simulations were performed with SERPENT 2.2 [12], using its continuous-energy Monte Carlo transport and depletion capabilities. The model specifications used in this work are summarized in Table I. The two-dimensional pin-cell was modeled with reflective boundary conditions to approximate the presence of surrounding fuel pins. A fine spatial discretization of the fuel pellet into four equi-volumetric depletion regions, together with a detailed time discretization of the irradiation history, the use of predictor-correctors and a sufficiently large number of Monte Carlo histories, ensured that the results were not affected by errors coming from model simplifications.

2.2. The REBUS Experimental Benchmark

To extend the analysis to experimental validation, a second case study was based on post-irradiation examination (PIE) data from the REBUS International Program (Reactivity Tests for a Direct Evaluation of the Burnup Credit on Selected Irradiated LWR Fuel Bundles)[5]. The program aimed to validate computational tools for criticality-safety analyses with burnup credit by providing benchmark-quality radiochemical assay data for spent PWR fuel, including measurements of actinide and fission-product concentrations.

The analyzed sample originates from fuel assembly 419 irradiated in the GKN II PWR reactor in Germany between August 1993 and August 1996 [13]. The examined sample is UO_2 fuel with an initial enrichment of 3.8 wt.% in ^{235}U , and a declared burnup of 54 GWd/t.

The benchmark model was implemented in SERPENT 2.2 using a two-dimensional representation of the full 18×18 fuel assembly. Reflective boundary conditions were applied on all sides to mimic the

Table I. TMI-1 pin-cell model specifications.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Fuel type	UO ₂ (4.85% in ²³⁵ U)	Cladding	Zircaloy 4
Coolant density	0.7484 g/cm ³	Specific power	33.58 W/gU
Pellet ∅	9.391 mm	Fuel division	4 radial regions
Pellet density	10.283 g/cm ³	Max BU step	0.5 GWd/t below 15 GWd/t, 2.5 GWd/t above 15 GWd/t
Cladding outer ∅	10.928 mm	Predictor-corrector	Constant extrapolation, Linear interpolation
Cladding thickness	0.673 mm	No. histories	100k/batch for 330 batches (of which 30 inactive)

surrounding assemblies. The rod corresponding to the measured sample (M11) is located in the central zone of the assembly, as shown in Figure 1 in dark red. Such a rod was divided into four radial equi-volumetric depletion regions. Each neighboring pin was also depleted independently of the rest of the fuel rods. In total, twelve fuel rods contained gadolinium oxide (Gd₂O₃) at 7 wt.%, each of which was also depleted separately using four equi-volumetric zones. The rest of the specifications were taken from the ORNL report in [13].

Figure 1. Two-dimensional fuel assembly model of the REBUS benchmark implemented in SERPENT 2.2. The rod corresponding to the measured sample (M11) is shown in dark red.

The irradiation history was simulated over four consecutive operating cycles (cycles 5–8), using cycle-averaged values of sample specific power, coolant density, and boron concentration derived from [13]. These irradiation parameters are listed in Table II.

2.3. Nuclear data libraries

All depletion calculations were performed under identical modelling conditions to isolate the impact of the nuclear data evaluations. Six libraries were considered, with three releases from both the JEFF and ENDF/B projects: JEFF-3.1.2, JEFF-3.3, JEFF-4.0, and ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, ENDF/B-VIII.1.

Minor adjustments were introduced to ensure compatibility across datasets and codes:

- For all libraries, the thermal scattering law (TSL) data were taken from JEFF-3.3.
- In ENDF/B-VIII.1, the ²³⁹Pu fission yield data were replaced with those from ENDF/B-VIII.0 due

Table II. Operating parameters used for simulating the irradiation history of the REBUS benchmark sample over four consecutive reactor cycles (5–8). The cumulative sample burnup (BU) was calculated at the end of each operating cycle.

Cycle	Sample Specific Power (W/gU)	Coolant Density (g/cm ³)	Boron Content (ppm)	Cycle Length (days)	Cumulative BU (MWd/kg)
5	56.265	0.646	477	310.0	17.44
6	47.634	0.665	579	386.7	35.86
7	40.820	0.681	479	347.9	50.06
8	11.626	0.725	553	346.8	54.09

to compatibility issues with SERPENT 2.2.

- For JEFF-3.1.2, decay and fission yield data were taken from JEFF-3.1.1, since they were not released at the time of the JEFF-3.1.2 evaluation [14].

A summary of the library components used in this study is presented in Table III.

Table III. Summary of nuclear data library components used in different evaluations. Bold entries indicate that the component corresponds to the main evaluated library. ACE: A-Compact ENDF (neutron files), TSL: Thermal Scattering Laws, NFY: Neutron-induced Fission product Yields, SFY: Spontaneous Fission product Yields, RDD: Radioactive Decay Data, BR: Branching Ratios.

	JEFF-3.1.2	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.0	ENDF/B-VIII.1
ACE	JEFF-3.1.2	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.0	ENDF/B-VIII.1
TSL	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3
NFY	JEFF-3.1.1	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.0	ENDF/B-VIII.1 (²³⁹ Pu from ENDF/B-VIII.0)
SFY	JEFF-3.1.1	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3	ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.0	ENDF/B-VIII.1
RDD	JEFF-3.1.1	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.0	ENDF/B-VIII.1
BR	JEFF-3.1.2	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.0	ENDF/B-VIII.1

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. TMI-1 Pin-Cell Case

The concentrations for nuclides important for spent fuel characterization for waste management purposes and burnup credit were calculated for the TMI-1 pin-cell case at 60 GWd/t, without considering decay after the end of irradiation, and they are compared across all nuclear data libraries. For each nuclide i , the predicted concentration obtained using a specific library j is denoted as $C_{i,j}$. To facilitate comparison among libraries, the results are standardized for each nuclide as follows:

$$X_{i,j} = \frac{C_{i,j} - \bar{C}_i}{\sigma_{C_i}}, \quad (1)$$

where \bar{C}_i and σ_{C_i} represent the mean and standard deviation of the predicted concentrations for nuclide i across all six libraries. This normalization removes the dependency on the absolute magnitude of the nuclide concentrations and highlights predictive trends in the form of deviations. It allows a preliminary comparison of the relative behavior of the nuclear data evaluations, even in the absence of experimental benchmarks. The standardized results are shown in Figure 2, with the predictions from

JEFF-4.0 highlighted using black markers.

Figure 2. Standardized concentrations $X_{i,j}$ for each nuclide i and library j in the TMI-1 pin-cell case at 60 GWd/t. JEFF-4.0 results are highlighted with black circles.

The nuclides on the horizontal axis are sorted in descending order of $X_{i,JEFF-4.0}$. Nuclides on the left correspond to cases where JEFF-4.0 predicts higher concentrations than the other libraries, while those on the right indicate lower predictions. Standardized values significantly larger than $+1$ or smaller than -1 suggest that the results obtained with JEFF-4.0 deviate substantially from the ensemble mean, revealing potential differences in the underlying nuclear data evaluations. This effect may be amplified for nuclides where several libraries share common evaluations, leading to artificially clustered results. In Figure 2 red and blue shades are used to highlight for what nuclides JEFF-4.0 systematically over-predicts or under-predicts, respectively, compared to “all” other considered nuclear data libraries.

For the TMI-1 pin-cell case, JEFF-4.0 systematically over-predicts — relative to the other libraries — the concentrations of ^{148}Sm , ^{150}Nd , ^{145}Nd , ^{234}U , ^{137}Cs , ^{237}Np , ^{151}Sm , ^{106}Ru , ^{144}Nd , and ^{90}Sr . Conversely, it under-predicts the concentrations of ^{233}U , ^{151}Eu , ^{155}Gd , ^{79}Se , ^{153}Eu , ^{107}Pd , ^{109}Ag , ^{109}Pd , ^{149}Sm , ^{152}Sm , ^{99}Tc , ^{103}Rh , ^{242}Pu , and ^{150}Sm .

These patterns are expected to persist in more realistic benchmark applications, demonstrating the value of this mock-up comparison as a diagnostic tool for identifying potential biases and guiding further improvements in nuclear data evaluations.

3.2. REBUS Experimental Benchmark

For the REBUS experimental case, the nuclide concentration predictions obtained with SERPENT 2.2 using different nuclear data libraries are compared against the experimental measurements reported in [13]. The measured nuclide concentrations are expressed in milligrams per gram of uranium in fresh fuel. The predicted concentrations are converted to relative deviations from the experimental values as:

$$R_{i,j} = \left(\frac{C_{i,j}}{E_i} - 1 \right) \times 100, \quad (2)$$

where E_i denotes the measured concentration of nuclide i . The results for the three JEFF libraries are presented in Figure 3, using the same color scheme adopted in Figure 2 for consistency.

Figure 3. Relative deviations $R_{i,j}$ of predicted nuclide concentrations from experimental measurements in the REBUS benchmark for the three JEFF libraries. Deviations are expressed in percent relative to measured values.

Except for palladium isotopes — known to exhibit discrepancies due to radiochemical dissolution challenges [13] — the maximum deviation across all libraries remains within 30%. For ^{235}U , ^{236}U , ^{238}U , ^{238}Pu , ^{240}Pu , ^{241}Pu , ^{245}Cm , ^{137}Cs , ^{143}Nd , ^{144}Nd , ^{146}Nd , ^{148}Nd , ^{147}Sm , ^{149}Sm and ^{154}Sm , the relative deviations are below 2% with JEFF-4.0. This reflects a notable improvement of JEFF-4.0 over previous releases, particularly for ^{238}Pu , ^{245}Cm , and several samarium isotopes, as well as key burnup indicators such as ^{137}Cs and ^{148}Nd , which previously exceeded 2% deviation in JEFF-3.3. These improvements are consistent with the introduction of updated fission yield evaluations in JEFF-4.0.

Caution is, however, advised when interpreting results for nuclides highly sensitive to operating or modeling assumptions, or with large uncertainties in measurements. For instance, ^{245}Cm is strongly influenced by moderator density (here taken as a cycle average), while improvements for samarium isotopes should be cross-checked with other nuclides in the promethium-samarium-europium transmutation chains. The improved predictions for ^{242}Cm and ^{242m}Am in JEFF-4.0 can be also attributed to the re-evaluated partial cross section of ^{241}Am to the metastable/ground state.

The over/under-predictions observed for JEFF-4.0 compared to other nuclear data libraries in the TMI-1 pin-cell are largely confirmed in the REBUS benchmark. Among other nuclides, ^{155}Gd , ^{153}Eu , ^{109}Ag , ^{152}Sm , ^{150}Sm , ^{145}Nd , ^{150}Nd , and ^{242}Pu follow similar patterns as in the pin-cell, confirming that the deviations identified in the mock-up case — between results obtained with JEFF-4.0 relative to previous JEFF releases — are also observed in the analysis of nuclide inventory experimental benchmarks. For all of these, except ^{109}Ag , JEFF-4.0 exhibits larger deviations from measurements, compared to the other JEFF libraries. These findings highlight that simple, well-defined computational benchmarks can serve as effective predictive tools for assessing nuclear data performance prior to experimental validation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the performance of the JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library was assessed for UO_2 fuel depletion calculations and compared against earlier JEFF releases (JEFF-3.1.2 and JEFF-3.3) as well as other major

evaluations (ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, and ENDF/B-VIII.1). The comparison was first carried out on the simplified TMI-1 PWR pin-cell model, designed to isolate the effects of nuclear data without system-specific modeling uncertainties, and then extended to the experimental REBUS benchmark.

The results specific for the REBUS benchmark show that JEFF-4.0 yields systematically improved agreement with experimental data for several key nuclides, in particular burnup indicators such as ^{137}Cs and ^{148}Nd , compared to those produced with older JEFF libraries.

Moreover, the analysis of standardized deviations in the TMI pin-cell case showed that several discrepancies across libraries can be understood even without experimental data. However, the comparison against experimental data remains necessary to identify which nuclear data library leads to better predictions. This approach provides an interpretable diagnostic tool for evaluating consistency among nuclear data evaluations and identifying potential anomalies in predictive trends.

Overall, JEFF-4.0 shows progress in nuclide prediction accuracy for spent fuel characterization, though some discrepancies remain for specific nuclides, such as ^{242}Pu and some samarium isotopes. Future work will extend this analysis to additional experimental datasets, including samples with different burnup and MOX fuels, to consolidate the validation of the new JEFF-4.0 evaluations.

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